

VISUAL IDENTITY

in Diamond Open Access publishing

Visual elements like logo, colours, typography, imagery, shape how readers perceive a publisher and its journals.

A strong visual identity communicates professionalism and quality at a glance.

Here are key strategies to enhance the visibility and perception you need to stand out and attract readership.

#1 - Thematic alignment: be relevant

- Visuals reflect the journal's subject matter.
e.g. earth tones for environmental journals.
- Logo embodies its core mission and values.

#2 - High quality: be appealing

- High-quality images and logos.
- Eye-catching graphics on social media.
- A well-designed website with easy navigation and clear content presentation.
- Professional design expertise – if resources allow.

#3 - Consistency: be recognizable

- Unified branded visual identity across all media, such as websites, email communications, social media, print publications and any marketing material (banners, brochures, presentations) for conferences and events.
- A comprehensive style guide outlining the use of logos, colors, typography and other visual elements, for all publications and marketing materials.